

THE INFLUENCE OF WORK VALUES AND ORGANIZATIONAL CULTURE ON EMPLOYEE CREATIVITY MEDIATED BY KNOWLEDGE SHARING (STUDY ON EMPLOYEES OF THE REGIONAL SECRETARIAT OF KONAWE REGENCY)

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Abstract

Creativity of organizational members (employees) is a hope for all types of organizations, because creativity will drive the dynamics and performance of the organization. Creativity can be influenced by several variables, including: work values, organizational culture and knowledge sharing. In several study results, knowledge sharing plays a role in mediating the influence of work values and organizational culture on creativity. This study aims to: analyze and evaluate the influence of work values and organizational culture on employee knowledge sharing and creativity, as well as the role of knowledge sharing in mediating the influence of work values and organizational culture on employee creativity at the Konawe Regency Regional Secretariat. The study population was 195 people with a sample of 131 people taken by cluster random sampling, in 13 parts of the research object. The data collection instrument used was a questionnaire. Data analysis was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistics with SmartPLS software version 4.0. Work values have a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, meaning that if work values improve, knowledge sharing will increase; 2) Work values have a positive and significant effect on employee creativity, meaning that if work values improve or increase, employee creativity will increase; 3) Work culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, which means that if the organizational culture, then knowledge sharing will increase; 4) Organizational culture has a positive but not significant effect on employee creativity, which means that the improvement or creation of organizational culture that is applied has not had a significant impact on increasing employee creativity; 5) Knowledge sharing has a positive but not significant effect on employee creativity, which means that the knowledge sharing that is currently applied has not been able to encourage increased employee creativity in this research object; 6) Knowledge sharing acts as a partial mediation on the effect of work values on employee creativity 7) Knowledge sharing acts as a partial mediation on the effect of organizational culture on employee creativity.

Keywords: Work Values, Organizational Culture, Knowledge Sharing, Creativity.

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee creativity is very important for every organization including public organizations such as local governments. Government organizations without creativity and innovation will impact organizational dynamics and will affect the overall performance of the organization. There have been many studies that focus on employee creative performance in the workplace (Ren et al, 2020; Liu et al. al., 2019; Martinaityte et al., 2019; Wallace et al., 2016).

Creativity as an important factor in determining the survival and development of an organization (Saad et al., 2015; Amabile, 1988). Employee creativity is considered as one of the important elements of organizational success and efficiency (Mumford et al, 2002). Therefore, creative behavior is the ability to create new ideas or thoughts in management such as developing new products (Ranjbar et al, 2019).

Theoretically, the creation of creativity can be influenced by several factors including: work values, organizational culture and also knowledge sharing. Several research results have proven this, such as research by Ren et al (2020) which found that employee work values have a significant impact on creative performance. Different work values will have different effects on work results.

Comfort as an indicator of work values has a significant negative impact on creative performance. Meanwhile, competency and status values have a positive and significant impact on creative performance. Comfort and competency values both directly affect creative performance, and they also have an indirect effect through the mediation of knowledge sharing.

Work values can affect employee creativity mediated by knowledge sharing (Ren et al., 2020). Knowledge sharing has a positive impact on the organization, because it can increase the flow of knowledge, information and skills between individuals and organizations and increase the level of creativity of the organization and individuals (Ma et al., 2017; Woodfield and Husted, 2017) and is reinforced by Rese et al (2020) that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity, as an emphasis on the findings of Ahmed et al (2016) and Lee (2018) that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. And it is also said that the quality of knowledge sharing is the main factor that facilitates individual creativity.

Knowledge sharing is a social process in which employees continuously contribute and collect ideas and solutions to problems from each other. They share work experiences, technical skills, and technological knowledge with other members of the organization (Lin, 2007), thus paving the way for creativity, innovation, and performance.

The process of knowledge sharing stimulates the generation of new ideas and thoughts when members are exposed to new ways of doing work (Aslam et al., 2013). Knowledge sharing can improve skills relevant to creativity (Perry-Smith & Shalley, 2003). Thus, it will increase the tendency of employees to be more creative and innovative in their work and roles. Knowledge sharing in an organization can increase the possibility of idea generation and creativity among employees (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2007).

However, in contrast to the findings of Rudawska (2020) that proactive and reactive knowledge sharing are not related to creativity and are not always positive for the creativity of the giver, but have an effect on organizational creativity. Therefore, it is important for organizations to encourage knowledge sharing that has an impact on employee creativity.

This condition should be cultivated in organizations as Ahmed et al (2016) suggests the importance of organizational culture, such as collaborative culture which has been proven to play a role in increasing organizational creativity through various dimensions of knowledge sharing (Ahmed et al., 2016).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Theoretical basis

The grand theory in this study is organizational theory. Miles (2012) stated that organization is a directing function by influencing employees to perform activities as well as possible. This activity includes leading, motivating and communicating with employees as individuals and as a group and as an organization.

Effective direction involves guiding and inspiring employees to achieve the vision and goals of the organization. Directing activities also include setting a good example for employees, serving as a role model and showing others the way to job success and organizational careers.

B. Criticism of Theory

Self-determination theory has been criticized on a number of different fronts. First, the theory has been called "Pollyannaish," because it focuses primarily on the positive, optimistic, "bright side" of life and tends to ignore the negative, pessimistic, "dark side" of most people's actual lives. Deci and Ryan (2000) responded by saying that the theory also focuses on the anxiety, sadness, and hostility that occur when basic needs are not met.

C. Implications of the theory for managers

Self-determination theory examines the extent to which a person's behavior is self-motivated or self-determined. When people meet their three basic needs for autonomy, relatedness, and competence, they tend to have higher levels of performance, health, and well-being than when they do not meet these three basic needs (Miles, 2012).

D. Organizational culture

Based on the grand theory of research, the substantive theory related to organizational culture variables is Institutional theory addresses the central question of why all organizations in a field tend to look and act the same (DiMaggio & Powell, 1983).

The core concept of institutional theory is that organizational structures and processes tend to acquire meaning and achieve stability in their own right, rather than based on their effectiveness and efficiency in achieving desired goals, such as the organization's mission and objectives (Lincoln, 1995). In the early stages of an organization's life cycle, there is considerable variation in organizational forms. However, over time, there is surprising homogeneity in organizational structures and practices.

The origins of social identity theory are rooted in the published works of Tajfel and Turner (1986). Originally intended as a social psychological approach used in explaining people's conceptualization and self-categorization of group membership, intergroup behavior, and general group processes, social identity theory is now considered one of the most critical theoretical frameworks used in the study of organizational science. Ashforth and Mael, 1989).

Focusing on social categorization, Tajfel (1978: 63) describes social identity as "an individual's knowledge that he or she belongs to a particular social group together with some emotional and value significance for him or her of this group membership".

Organizational culture is a set of norms and values that are widely shared and held throughout an organization (O'Reilly and Chatman, 1996; Guiso et al., 2015). Interest in organizational culture owes to the recognition of its role in ensuring firm performance (O'Reilly, 2014). As organizational goals become more specific over the long term, organizations become more formalized and institutionalized.

The development of organizational values, beliefs, and practices ensures the differentiation of an organization from others and can determine its success.

E. Hypothesis

- H1: Work values have a positive and significant influence on knowledge sharing
- H2: Work values have a positive and significant influence on employee creativity.
- H3: Organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on knowledge sharing
- H4: Organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on employee creativity.
- H5: Knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity
- H6: Knowledge sharing plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of work values on employee creativity.
- H7: Knowledge sharing plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee creativity.

III. METHOD

The populations in this study were Civil Servants of the Konawe Regency Regional Government who worked at the Regional Secretariat, totaling 195 people. The number of samples was 131 people taken by cluster random sampling, from 13 sections in the research object. The data collection method used in this study was using a list of questions in the form of a questionnaire distributed to respondents (employees of the Konawe Regency Regional Secretariat) related to the variables discussed in this study.

Analysis of the research data was carried out using descriptive and inferential statistics using SmartPLS software version 4.0. which is run on a computer media. The reasons for using smart PLS are: PLS is a powerful analysis method that is not based on many assumptions. Smart PLS ver 4 is easy to operate, and can process data simultaneously, both direct and mediation effects and its output can display the p-value of direct effect and indirect effect.

IV. RESULTS

A. Outer Model

The measurement model or Outer Model in PLS is used to ensure that the indicators (reflective) used truly reflect or form latent variables with validity and reliability. In the outer model testing is done to determine the relationship between indicators (formed from items) with latent variables. Outer model testing uses the values: 1) convergent validity as seen from the outer loading value; 2) discriminant validity, as seen from the AVE value, and 3) composite reliability.

B. Convergent Validity

Outer model testing based on convergent validity can be seen from the outer loading value. The outer loading value of all variable indicators used is as shown in table 1.

Table 1: Outer Loading Values

Variables	Indicator	Outer Loading	Cut Off
Work Values	X11 Comfort	0,909419	0,70
	X12 Competence	0,914054	
	X13 Status	0,930690	
Organizational culture	X21 Group Culture	0,858569	
	X22 Adhocracy Culture	0,907170	
	X23 Rational Culture	0,911531	
	X24 Hierarchical Culture	0,874118	
Sharing Knowledge	Y11 Intensity	0,931793	
	Y12 Quality	0,931073	
Employee Creativity	Y21 Novelty	0,967135	
	Y22 Utility	0,975168	

Source: Primary Data (processed)

The results of the analysis as seen in Table 1, show that the outer loading value for each indicator is above 0.70, meaning that all indicators used have a strong correlation with the latent variables, so it can be said that all indicators used are the main formers of the variables used in this research model.

C. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity testing is carried out to ensure that concepts or measurements that should not be related are indeed not significantly correlated. The value used in reflective indicators is the Cross loading value of all constructs.

The indicator must have the highest loading on the construct being measured and must be higher than the indicator loading on other constructs. Testing can also be done by comparing the Square root of Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each variable with the correlation between other variables in the model.

If the AVE of a variable is greater than the correlation with all other variables, it means that it has good discriminant validity, and its value must be greater than 0.50. The results of the cross loading and AVE analysis can be displayed in table 2.

Table 2: Cross Loading and AVE Values

Variables	Indicator	BO_X2	NK_X1	SP_Y1	KP_Y2	AVE
Work Values	X11 Comfort	0,739751	0,909419	0,689391	0,710190	0,755
	X12 Competence	0,702329	0,914054	0,662401	0,864803	
	X13 Status	0,850794	0,930690	0,741595	0,825472	
Organizational culture	X21 Group Culture	0,858569	0,702210	0,727934	0,689179	
	X22 Adhocracy Culture	0,907170	0,757979	0,756073	0,726147	
	X23 Rational Culture	0,911531	0,764836	0,763459	0,730609	
	X24 Hierarchical Culture	0,874118	0,718181	0,613237	0,656829	
Sharing Knowledge	Y11 Intensity	0,722275	0,671734	0,931793	0,638834	
	Y12 Quality	0,789341	0,74134	0,931073	0,732606	
Employee Creativity	Y21 Novelty	0,765421	0,877668	0,745356	0,967135	
	Y22 Utility	0,771643	0,825774	0,688634	0,975168	

Source: Primary Data (processed)

The data from the analysis of table 2 shows that: from the cross loading value for each latent variable indicator is greater than the value of other latent variable indicators which are marked with a bold value greater than the value next to it, meaning it already has good discriminant validity.

Likewise, if using an AVE value of 0.755 is greater than the minimum AVE value requirement of 0.50. Thus, it can be said that the model used has good discriminant validity.

D. R-Squared (R²)

R-Squared is a measurement that shows how much variation in endogenous latent variables can be explained by exogenous latent variables.

A higher R-Squared value indicates a better model. The results of the R-square analysis are shown in table 3.

Table 3: R2 AVE Test Results

Variable	Type	R ²	R ² _adj	Ave
NK (X1)	Exogenous	0	0	0,842907
BO (X2)	Exogenous	0	0	0,788767
SP (Y1)	Endogenous	0,68168	0,676706	0,867568
KP (Y2)	Endogenous	0,782955	0,777828	0,943151

Source: Primary Data (processed)

Table 3 data shows that the value of R2 is 0.68168 for Y1 and 0.782955 for Y2. This means that 68.16% of the Y1 variable (knowledge sharing) and 78.29% of the Y2 variable (employee creativity) as endogenous variables are influenced by exogenous variables, namely: work values (X1) and organizational culture (X2).

E. Predictive Relevance (Q Squared)

Predictive Relevance (Q-Squared) is a statistical test that measures the predictive ability of a model. A high and positive Q-Squared value means that the model used has good predictive ability. The results of the analysis show that the Q-Squared value = 0.9309102704028575 or rounded to 0.94.

The magnitude of this value indicates that the model used in this study has better and more accurate predictive ability. Based on the results of the R-Squared (R2) and Predictive Relevance (Q2) tests, it can be concluded that the model used is a good model (fit) because the exogenous variables used have a high ability to explain and predict endogenous variables.

F. Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing is carried out by comparing the P-Value with alpha 5% or 0.05 on each coefficient of direct influence and indirect influence and mediation and conceptually showing the relationship between variables along with the magnitude of the direct and indirect path coefficients and the mediation effect, which can be clearly shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Diagram of Research Model Analysis Results

Hypothesis 1: It is suspected that Work Value has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing. The results of the analysis of the direct influence path coefficient related to hypothesis 1 (H1) obtained a positive coefficient value of 0.273833 or 27.38% which indicates the magnitude of the direct influence between the work value variable (X1) on the knowledge sharing variable (Y1), with a p-value of 0.003 < 0.05, meaning that work value (X1) has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, thus the first hypothesis is proven true or accepted.

Hypothesis 2: It is suspected that Work Value has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. The results of the analysis of the direct influence between the work value variable (X1) on the employee creativity variable (Y2) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.671137 or 67.11% with a p-value of 0.000 smaller than alpha 0.05 (0.000 < 0.05). This means that the work value variable (X1) has a positive and significant effect on the employee creativity variable (Y2), thus, the second hypothesis proposed is proven true or accepted.

Hypothesis 3: It is suspected that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing. The results of the analysis of the direct influence between the organizational culture variable (X2) on the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.584196 or 58.42% with a p-value of 0.000 or less than alpha 5% (0.000 < 0.05). This means that the organizational culture variable (X2) has a positive and significant effect on the knowledge sharing variable (Y1). Thus, the third hypothesis is proven true or accepted.

Hypothesis 4: It is suspected that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. The results of the analysis of the direct influence between the organizational culture variable (X2) on the employee creativity variable (Y2) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.147500 or 14.75% with a p-value of 0.087 greater than alpha 5% or 0.05 (0.087 > 0.05). This means that the organizational

culture variable (X2) has a positive but insignificant effect on the employee creativity variable (Y2). Thus, the fourth hypothesis proposed is not proven true or is rejected.

Hypothesis 5: It is suspected that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. The results of the analysis of the direct influence between the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) on the employee creativity variable (Y2) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.107369 or 10.74% with a p-value of 0.145 greater than alpha 5% or 0.05 ($0.14 > 0.05$). This means that the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) has a positive but insignificant effect on the employee creativity variable (Y2). Thus, the fifth hypothesis proposed is not proven true or rejected.

Hypothesis 6: It is assumed that "knowledge sharing plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of work values on employee creativity". The results of the analysis of the indirect influence between the work value variable (X1) on the employee creativity variable (Y2) mediated by the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.029401 or 2.94% with a p-value of 0.000 smaller than 0.05, meaning that the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of the work value variable (X1) on the employee creativity variable (Y2). Thus, the sixth hypothesis is proven true or accepted, but its role is partial, because the indirect or mediation effect is smaller than the direct effect, which is 0.029401 or 2.94% < 0.671137 or 67.11%. Even though it has a partial role, the existence of knowledge sharing as a mediating variable is still important, because it still has a total effect that is greater than the direct influence, namely 0.700538 or 70.05% > 67.11%.

Hypothesis 7: It is suspected that knowledge sharing plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee creativity. The results of the analysis of the indirect influence between the organizational culture variable (X2) on the employee creativity variable (Y2) through the mediation of the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) obtained a positive path coefficient of 0.062725 or 6.27% with a p-value of 0.002 smaller than alpha 0.05. This means that the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of organizational culture (X2) on the employee creativity variable (Y2). Thus, the seventh hypothesis is proven true or accepted, but its role is partial, because the indirect influence is smaller than the direct influence, which is 0.062725 or 6.27% < 0.147500 or 14.75%. Even though it has a partial role, the existence of knowledge sharing as a mediating variable in the influence of organizational culture (X2) on employee creativity (Y2) is still important, because it still has a total effect that is greater than the direct influence, namely 0.210225 or 21.02% > 14.75%.

V. DISCUSSION

A. The Influence of Work Values on Knowledge Sharing

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing indicate that the perceived work value through the comfort, competence and status indicators has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing perceived through the intensity and quality indicators indicated by the influence coefficient value of 27.38%. This condition is caused by the high work value with an average of 4.32 which has also been followed by the high value of the knowledge sharing variable with an average of 4.25 and both are in the good category. The main cause is the status indicator with an average of 4.39 which is formed by: 1) very good interaction with fellow co-workers with an

average of 4.52; 2) cooperation between employees with an average of 4.44; and 3) good understanding of work goals with an average of 4.43. It can be said that the status of work values has been created well through good interaction between fellow co-workers, because it is supported by good cooperation between fellow employees as co-workers.

The creation of good work values, especially the creation of status has encouraged good knowledge sharing, especially in knowledge that is shared easily understood, accurate and relevant to the work carried out where all are valued well or above 4.0. Likewise, it also has an impact on the intensity of knowledge sharing through the frequency of sharing knowledge with a value of 4.31 voluntarily with a value of 4.27, and often sharing knowledge with other work units with a value of 4.17. This condition indicates that employees have often shared knowledge among themselves and done voluntarily, including with other work units, but still need improvement in terms of both intensity and quality.

This finding strengthens the results of Baskoro's study (2021) which found that work values have a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing. Because values are a kind of belief (Hackman and Oldham, 1980), inspire individual intrinsic motivation (Meglino and Ravlin, 1998), and influence work results by changing their behavior (Kirkman and Shapiro, 2001). Work values can influence a person's work behavior as Locke and Henne (1986) suggest that work values influence employee work behavior, which in turn affects the quantity and quality of work produced.

B. The Influence of Work Values on Employee Creativity

It was found that the work value variable (X1) had a positive and significant effect on the employee creativity variable (Y2) which was perceived through the indicators of novelty and usefulness with an influence coefficient of 67.11%. The significance of the influence of work values on employee creativity in the research object, because the creation of good work values through the creation of comfort in the workplace and having good competence related to work, and what is important is the status of good understanding of work as the main determinant of work values formed through: 1) interaction between coworkers, 2) cooperation between coworkers, 3) good understanding of the objectives of the work unit, 4) flexibility of working hours, and 5) the existence of superior appreciation for the work results achieved.

Meanwhile, the competency indicators formed through: 1) employee ability to adapt to changes in the work environment, 2) employees generally already have technical skills in carrying out work; 3) the ability to formulate effective solutions related to work. Likewise, the comfort indicator formed by the existence of good incentives in the workplace that has provided good comfort for employees has had an impact on good perceptions of employee creativity through the novelty indicator with an average of 4.22 and the usefulness indicator with an average of 4.24 and both are the main and right shapers for employee creativity variables. This condition empirically causes a positive and significant influence between the work value variable and employee creativity in the object of this study.

This finding supports the results of previous studies, as Lin et al. (2015b) and Sonnentag et al. (2020) found that work values are closely related to employee creativity, because work values serve as evaluative standard functions, which are needed for employees to identify what is right when making work-related decisions. However, this finding again corrects some of the results of Ren et al. (2020) who found

that the value of job comfort and security as an indicator of work values had a significant negative effect on creative performance. Although it was also found that the indicators of work competence and growth (competence) and work status and independence (status) had a significant positive effect on creative performance. This finding is consistent and at the same time strengthens the theory about the relationship between work values and creativity, where increasing work values through increasing comfort, competence, and status has a positive impact on increasing employee creativity which is reflected in novelty and usefulness.

C. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Knowledge Sharing

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing found that the organizational culture variable (X2) reflected through: group culture, adhocracy culture, rational culture, and hierarchy culture has a positive and significant effect on the knowledge sharing variable (Y1) with an influence coefficient value of 58.42%.

Phenomenally, this finding can be explained that the creation of a conducive work culture, both in group culture, adhocracy culture, rational culture, and hierarchy culture, all of which are perceived well by respondents, has had an impact on good knowledge sharing, where employees are able to share knowledge that is easy to understand, accurate, and relevant to work. A good work culture has also had an impact on the frequency of sharing knowledge among employees, voluntarily with employees from other units.

The creation of a good organizational culture is seen in the indicators of hierarchical culture through: 1) employee compliance with established rules, 2) implementation of a work system that is in accordance with the structure, and 3) provision of good service. In group culture because of: 1) employee solidarity in completing tasks, 2) providing mutual support in completing tasks, and 3) involvement in open discussions to reach mutual agreements, and in adhocracy culture it is seen from: 1) the ability to solve problems creatively, 2) providing new ideas to improve services, and 3) employees are adaptive to change. While in rational culture because: 1) employees work to outperform other work units, 2) efforts to achieve targets, and 3) appreciation for achievements achieved by colleagues.

This finding strengthens the results of a study conducted by Memon et al (2020) which found that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, because organizational culture is able to encourage the exchange of ideas between employees through social interactions in the workplace facilitating knowledge transfer and other researchers also found a positive and significant impact between organizational culture and knowledge sharing (Poul et al., 2016; Islam et al., 2011).

The creation of a good organizational culture will encourage the creation of a good working atmosphere, so that the desire to share knowledge among fellow members of the organization in order to overcome work problems that are their duties will increase. Therefore, organizational culture is considered an important factor in achieving business success, including the implementation of sustainability based on an approach that promotes the achievement of the company's social, environmental, and economic goals (Deal & Kennedy, 1982).

Organizational culture as a common belief and values of organizational culture. Tichy (1982) explores that organizational culture unites organizations as normative glue. Hodgetts and Luthans (2003) explore the different characteristics of organizational

culture. Organizational culture stimulates innovative behavior (Cameron and Quinn, 1999; Denison, 1990; Deshpande and Webster, 1989; Miron et al., 2004). Finally, it can be said that this finding reinforces the results of previous studies which concluded that organizational culture through indicators of group culture, adhocracy culture, rational culture, and hierarchical culture can influence organizational sharing and also the creativity of the organization's members themselves (Hamzah et al, 2020, Gregory et al, 2009, Denison and Spreitzer, 1991).

D. The Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Creativity

The results of the analysis show that organizational culture (X2) reflected through: group culture, adhocracy culture, rational culture and hierarchy culture has a positive but insignificant effect on employee creativity variables (Y2) perceived through indicators of novelty and usefulness with an influence of 14.75%. The insignificant effect of organizational culture on employee creativity is because a conducive organizational culture, through group culture, adhocracy culture, rational culture, and hierarchy culture that are perceived as good, has not had a significant impact on increasing employee creativity through indicators of novelty formed by the courage to take risks in completing new things is still low with a value of only 3.85, while the indicator of usefulness through its constituent items is still very low, namely the creative ideas of employees with a value of 3.32.

This finding is not in line with the results of previous studies such as those conducted by Ali-Taha et al (2016) who found that organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on creativity. Thus, an organizational culture that stimulates and promotes creativity and innovation is a must for organizations seeking competitive advantage. Also supporting the results of Ogbeibu's (2018) study, which found that adhocracy culture has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. Valencia et al. (2010) further emphasized that adhocracy culture involves exploring new opportunities and employee freedom to take calculated risks. Lau and Ngo (2004) also pointed out that this is a type of organizational culture that reflects employee participation, shared responsibility.

However, this finding is in line with the results of Gupta's (2011) research which states that organizational culture, especially hierarchical culture, does not have a significant effect on employee creativity. Likewise, Singh & Chaudari's (2018) research found that organizational culture does not have a significant effect on creativity.

In order to improve maximum service to the community through increased creativity, a strong organizational culture must be maintained and/or continuously improved, through management commitment by linking its decisions with beliefs in the organizational culture it adheres to, such as behavior of togetherness and responsibility for organizational development in the form of excellent service to increase community satisfaction.

E. The Influence of Knowledge Sharing on Employee Creativity

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing found that knowledge sharing reflected through intensity and quality indicators has a positive but not significant effect on employee creativity reflected through novelty and usefulness indicators, with a magnitude of influence of only 10.74%.

The insignificant effect of knowledge sharing on employee creativity is caused by the improvement in knowledge sharing not being balanced by an increase in employee creativity. This condition is seen phenomenally that knowledge sharing reflected by the intensity indicator formed by: 1) the high intensity of knowledge shared among employees with a value of 4.31 and the quality indicator formed by 2) the knowledge shared is easy to understand with a value of 4.33 has not been able to increase employee creativity reflected by the novelty indicator formed by the courage to take risks in completing new things which is only perceived as 3.85 and also on the usefulness indicator formed by promoting ideas to others which is only perceived with a value of 4.13.

The high creativity of employees on the novelty indicator formed by the item showing creativity in work when given the opportunity with a value of 4.34, is not caused by knowledge sharing formed by the intensity of knowledge shared and not because of the item of easy understanding of the knowledge shared, but because of the intensity of voluntary knowledge sharing and sharing knowledge with others, as well as the relevance of the knowledge shared with the work being done. This finding is in line with the results of Rudawska's (2020) study which revealed that proactive and reactive knowledge sharing are not related to creativity and that sharing knowledge with others is not always positive for the creativity of the individual giver, but has an effect on organizational creativity.

This finding is not in line with previous research findings and theories that say that knowledge sharing affects the creativity of organizational members. The results of the study by Ahmed et al (2016) found that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity. The role of knowledge provides organizations with sustainable competitive advantage and superior performance (Bajwa, Kitchlew, Sair, & Shahzad, 2015).

The capacity of an organization to be creative and innovative depends on the knowledge sharing that occurs within and across departments and divisions (Marouf & Khalil, 2015). Lee (2018) found that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity, and the quality of knowledge sharing is a major factor that facilitates individual creativity. Because knowledge sharing is a social process in which employees continuously contribute and collect ideas and solutions to each other's problems. They share work experiences, technical skills, and technological knowledge with other members of the organization (Lin, 2007), thus paving the way for creativity, innovation, and performance.

The process of knowledge sharing stimulates the generation of new ideas and thoughts when members are exposed to new ways of doing work (Aslam et al., 2013). Knowledge sharing can improve skills relevant to creativity (Perry-Smith & Shalley, 2003) and thus increase the tendency of employees to be more creative and innovative in their jobs and roles. Sharing knowledge within an organization can increase the possibility of idea generation and creativity among employees (De Jong & Den Hartog, 2007), and furthermore the knowledge and skills acquired will increase creativity (Gardner, 2012).

F. The Role of Knowledge Sharing in Mediating the Influence of Work Values on Employee Creativity

The results of the analysis and testing found that knowledge sharing plays a positive and significant role in mediating the influence of work values on employee creativity in

this research object, although the nature of the influence is partial, because the direct influence of work values on employee creativity is greater than through mediation of knowledge sharing, where the magnitude of the direct influence of 67.11% is greater than the indirect influence of 2.94%. Although its role is partial, the existence of knowledge sharing as a mediating variable is still important, because it still has a total effect that is greater than the direct influence, namely 70.05% > 67.11%.

This finding strengthens the results of research conducted by Ren et al. (2020) which found that knowledge sharing plays a role in mediating the influence of work values on employee creativity. Work values can influence employee creativity mediated by knowledge sharing. Knowledge sharing has a positive impact on the organization, because it can increase the flow of knowledge, information and skills between individuals and organizations and increase the level of creativity of the organization and individuals (Ma et al., 2017; Woodfield and Husted, 2017).

Research by Rese et al (2020) found that knowledge sharing has a positive and significant effect on employee creativity, because the dissemination of specific knowledge triggers the organizational learning process (Riege, 2005), new ideas and increases product and technology development, which strengthens the innovative capacity of individuals and organizations (Hung et al., 2011). This finding also strengthens the conclusion of Dwi BB (2021) that knowledge sharing plays a mediator between the comfort and status dimensions of work values towards creative performance. This study provides information on the influence of work values on the creative performance of the construction industry and confirms the role of knowledge sharing in mediating the dimensions of work values.

G. The Role of Knowledge Sharing in Mediating the Influence of Organizational Culture on Employee Creativity

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing found that knowledge sharing plays a role in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee creativity, although its role is partial, because the direct influence is greater than the indirect influence, which is 14.75% > 6.27%. Although its role is partial, the existence of knowledge sharing in mediating the influence of organizational culture variables on employee creativity is still important, because the total effect obtained is still greater than the direct influence, which is 21.02% > 14.75%.

The role of knowledge sharing in mediating the influence of organizational culture on employee creativity means that to increase employee creativity, it is necessary to: 1) create a conducive organizational culture through the creation of a compact group culture, openness in discussion and providing mutual support in carrying out tasks; 2) create an adhocracy culture through adaptation to an ever-changing environment, come up with new ideas, and must always be creative in solving problems; 3) create a culture of rationality related to the work done related to the targets to be achieved, appreciate the achievements of others, and always strive with high motivation to outperform the work unit; 4) create a hierarchical culture through compliance with the rules set by the organization, increase control over work processes and services, and always implement work processes that are in accordance with the existing structure.

This finding supports previous research findings that organizational culture plays a role in promoting knowledge sharing behavior and has received much attention lately (Ismail Al-Alawi, et al., 2007). Creativity researchers such as Gilson, Lim, Luciano, &

Choi (2013). have identified a significant impact of organizational culture on knowledge sharing behavior.

Organizational researchers have recognized that organizational culture is a powerful driver of knowledge sharing that further enables organizations to be creative and innovative (Nonaka & Takeuchi, 1995; Shahzad, Bajwa, Siddiqi, Ahmid, & Sultani, 2016). Organizations that successfully create, disseminate, and enhance knowledge rely heavily on shared practices, values, and beliefs that shape the culture and knowledge sharing behaviors of their members (Lau & Ngo, 2004).

Research Findings

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing based on the novelty of this research model which adds organizational culture variables as exogenous variables to the knowledge sharing variables and employee creativity as endogenous variables, it was found that: 1) Organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, but is not significant on employee creativity; 2) Knowledge sharing acts as a partial mediation between both work value variables and organizational culture variables on employee creativity.

Limitations of Research Results

The results of this study cannot be generalized to other objects or locations, because: 1) the study was only conducted at the regional secretariat, in Konawe Regency, Southeast Sulawesi Province, in addition to the data collected only at one point in time (cross-section); 2) this study has not considered internal organizational environmental factors such as leadership, while work values, organizational culture, knowledge sharing and creativity can be influenced by these variables. Thus, further research should pay more attention to the effects of these factors.

VI. CONCLUSION

The results of the analysis and hypothesis testing found that: 1) work values have a positive and significant effect on both knowledge sharing and employee creativity, but are not significant on; 2) work culture has a positive and significant effect on knowledge sharing, but is not significant on employee creativity; 3) knowledge sharing has a positive effect, but is not significant on employee creativity; 4) knowledge sharing acts as a partial mediation on the effect of work values on employee creativity; 5) knowledge sharing acts as a partial mediation on the effect of organizational culture on employee creativity.

Based on the results of the analysis of the variable description and conclusions, it is recommended that the Regional Secretariat Office of Konawe Regency: 1) needs to increase work values by increasing work comfort through increasing incentives and creating a balance between work and personal life; 2) needs to create a conducive rational culture by increasing motivation to outdo other work units; 3) needs to increase knowledge sharing among employees including in other work units so that organizational goals can be achieved.

Based on the limitations, conclusions and suggestions of the research results, the recommendations for further researchers are: 1) to review the existence of the knowledge sharing variable indicator as a mediating variable, because its mediation is only partial, both from work values and from organizational culture to creativity, through adjusting the indicator to the research object; 2) because organizational

culture is not significant to employee creativity, it is necessary to review the validity of the indicator and its constituent items; 3) to add leadership variables as exogenous variables in increasing employee creativity, because in theory good leadership can influence work values and a conducive organizational culture as well as knowledge sharing which can ultimately influence creativity.

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